

Book of Abstracts

Symposium on the Present and Future of Plant-Based Fermented Foods

Exploring Microbial, Technological, Health, and
Social Dimensions of Plant-based Fermented Foods

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Edited by:

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Editorial: Multiple dimensions of fermented plant-based foods

Armando Perez-Cueto

Umeå, February 12th, 2026

Fermentation stands out as a fundamental link connecting traditional practices with modern innovations. In the North, fermentation has long been used as a method to preserve and prolong the shelf life of scarce resources such as meat, fish, dairy, and fruit. Today, fermentation is moving forward and has become a key element in the future of food.

The *Symposium on the Present and Future of Plant-Based Fermented Foods* took place on September 8th, 2025, as a satellite event to HealthFerm's General Assembly in Umeå. Its intention was to highlight the work of the talented researchers involved in the project and to provide an opportunity for many early-stage researchers to publicly report their findings, exchange knowledge, network, and discuss the latest advancements in the field. This Abstracts Book is therefore a tribute to their efforts and scientific contributions.

The Symposium brought together cutting-edge science and cultural perspectives to explore fermentation as a driver of sustainable and health-promoting food systems. Centered on microbial and fermentation processes, the program highlighted how traditional and emerging techniques shape nutritional quality, sensory experience, and consumer trust. By integrating fermentation and health benefits with industry trends, consumer insights, and the ethnography of fermentation, the symposium created a rare interdisciplinary space where microbiology, food science, social science, and market realities intersected.

Keynote contributions anchored this dialogue at the forefront of research and innovation. Professor D. Nielsen (University of Copenhagen), coordinator of PROFERMENT, addressed how *Bacillus* and moulds enhance both the nutritional value and eating quality of plant-based fermented foods. Complementing this, Associate Professor D. Giacalone (University of Southern Denmark), coordinator of FlavourFerm, examined how sensory quality and personal factors shape diverse perceptions and acceptance of fermented plant-based foods. Together, these perspectives underscored fermentation not only as a technical process, but also as a lived, sensory, and culturally embedded practice critical to the future of plant-based diets.

Some take-home messages from the Symposium should encourage you to read the abstracts: fiber type and food matrix shape metabolic responses and should be considered together with sensory characteristics in the development of future foods. Integrating social science approaches with traditional consumer studies provides deeper insight into the social conditions shaping acceptance of fermented plant-based foods. The application of sensometrics proved essential for refining complex metabolomics data and identifying sensory-relevant compounds that drive consumer acceptance.

Enjoy the reading!

Fiber-Protein Interactions in Plant-Based Foods: Impacts on Digestibility, Glycemic Response, and Gut Microbiota

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The health benefits of plant-based diets are often attributed to their fiber content, which modulates protein metabolism and gut-derived effects. Our review highlighted that fermentable fiber may reduce harmful proteolytic fermentation, suggesting that fiber, and not just protein source, plays a central role in health outcomes of protein rich foods. However, the effects of different fiber types on protein metabolism remain unclear.

To explore this further, we conducted a systematic scoping review of 98 studies, focusing on clinical postprandial and in vitro digestion data. Results showed that plant proteins lead to slower amino acid absorption and reduced glucose responses compared to animal proteins, particularly when combined with fiber. In vitro findings emphasized the importance of the food matrix and processing methods, such as fermentation, in enhancing protein digestibility. Despite these insights, the role of gut microbiota in mediating these effects remains underexplored.

Building on these findings, we conducted a human intervention study with 17 participants at risk for metabolic syndrome. Participants consumed products with intrinsic or extrinsic fiber. Product B (extrinsic fiber) led to significantly lower glucose and insulin levels and showed more efficient protein hydrolysis in vitro.

These results highlight the importance of fiber type and food matrix in shaping metabolic responses and support the development of sustainable, health-promoting plant-based foods.

Deciphering the impact of varied grains and inocula on the metabolomic and sensory profile of fermentation prototypes

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Albeit the association of fermented foods with anti-nutritional factor decrement and bio-active compound transformation, legitimate data to validate these probable beneficial effects are scarce. Alternatively, widely available grains are underutilised, pertaining to novel product development due to conservative processing approaches. The aim of this study, a part of the Swiss Confederation and European Union co-funded HealthFerm project, is to develop novel fermented prototypes using different inocula and varied grains to decode the transformation of bio-active metabolites over time and corroborate their impact on flavour profile.

Herein, savoury sponge combinations were developed using target flours (100%- faba bean, oat, wheat, and rye) and chosen starters (70% buttermilk, 40% yoghurt, and 25% curd), through an in-house microwave steaming method. The incubation period was 24 hours at 30-degree C. Next, the prototypes (and intermediates, where relevant) were analysed for volatile compounds using HS(SPME)-GCMS and descriptive sensory evaluation with a semi-trained panel (n=9). Further, non-targeted metabolomic profiling using the Notame metabolomics workflow (UHPLC-QTOF-MS), and viscosity using a rheometer (PP20/ P2 serrated geometry assembly), and textural profiling with TPA are ongoing with an expected completion in July. The final step shall be to associate these analyses utilising regression models.

About 79 volatile compounds with odour attributes were identified, wherein aldehyde was the most abundant functional group over all samples. The sensory panel perceived buttermilk and yoghurt sponge combinations as sour flavoured and chewy textured for all flours, respectively (except faba bean, in the latter). Please note that a comprehensive dive into the remaining analyses results over summer will provide substantial evidence in determining the influence of metabolomic transformation on flavour profile alteration. The developed prototypes shall enable European citizens to transition towards a more sustainable diet with low reliance on animal-based proteins.

Impact of Drying Techniques on Sensory and Functional Properties of Fermented Faba Bean Protein Concentrates

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Plant-based meat alternatives are a climate-friendly option but typical protein ingredients like faba beans have off-flavours, such as beany flavour and bitterness, that limit their use. Fermentation and appropriate postprocessing steps could mitigate these off-flavours.

This study explored the combined efficacy of fermentation and different drying techniques on the sensory and functional properties of faba bean protein concentrates (FPC). The drying methods investigated include lyophilization, oven drying, and drum drying. The FPC was fermented with *Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus* at 40°C for 24h, dried, and extruded with pea protein isolate to create meat analogues. The fermented FPC flours and extrudates were then analyzed for sensory, chemical, and techno-functional properties, and modelled with multivariate statistics.

Fermentation decreased beany flavour and bitterness, and increased umami taste and related compounds. Heat-based drying decreased fermentation-related flavours in favour of cereal and roasted notes. Drum drying resulted in longer fibrils and higher tearing force, supported by lowest protein solubility and highest water binding capacity. The *in vitro* digestibility of the extrudates was comparable to chicken control, indicating no significant impact of drying method on protein digestibility.

In conclusion, the combination of fermentation and heat-based drying is a beneficial approach for producing high-quality meat analogues from faba bean protein concentrate.

Questioning the consumer acceptance of plant-based fermented food: the added value of the socio-ethnographic approach

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Transitioning to sustainable food systems often necessitates the adoption of new food products, particularly plant-based alternatives. A critical challenge in this transition is fostering consumer acceptance of novel ingredients. Many studies addressing this issue rely on behavioral economics and sensory science within "consumer studies", equating acceptance with "willingness to try" and consumption with rational "choice". However, these approaches often neglect the broader social and cultural contexts, reducing them to variables like attitudes or beliefs. The composition of a food repertoire is highly related to social and cultural dimensions of living, and cannot be studied at the individual level without considering these collective aspects.

That's the reason why sociological and anthropological methods can more effectively capture food acceptance as the regular integration of new products into dietary habits. Social sciences have indeed developed the ability to understand the complexity of individual practices embedded in the social life of a group. Ethnography and sociological qualitative methods allow to understand the way the materials, meanings and competences are linked within a specific set of practices.

Through their ability to reveal the social conditions of specific food acceptance, social sciences appear as a good complementarity to more classic consumer studies. This complementarity is visible in the workpackage 4 of the EU project HealthFerm, where both approaches are joint and collaborating in order to assess the consumer acceptance of fermented plant-based foods.

Decoding faba bean off-flavors: integrating metabolomics and sensory data through computational approaches

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Faba bean ingredients are emerging as sustainable protein sources, yet their adoption in food applications remains constrained by off-flavors that hinder consumer acceptance. This study integrates metabolomics with sensory science to elucidate potential molecular basis of off-flavors in commercial faba bean ingredients. Sensory profiling was conducted using Generic Descriptive Analysis with a trained panel (n=10), reference samples, and three evaluation sessions in a sensory laboratory conforming to ISO 8589 standards. Non-targeted metabolomics was performed via UHPLC-qTOF-MS/MS, employing hydrophilic interaction chromatography and reversed-phase chromatography in positive and negative electrospray ionization modes. A key challenge in this approach is feature selection, as the initial dataset contained over 14,000 signals, which were systematically refined using hierarchical cluster analysis, volcano plots, and fold-change analysis to pinpoint the most relevant sensory-related metabolites. Principal Component Analysis was used to assess metabolomic variation across samples, while Partial Least Squares Regression linked metabolites to sensory attributes. A total of 115 metabolites were identified, with choline, vicine, and betaine among the most abundant. Five metabolite clusters suggested cultivar-specific and process-related differences. Compounds such as caprolactam, gingerglycolipid, lysine, vicine, and histidyllysine were associated with bitterness and mouth-drying orosensation. To validate associations with bitter, sweet, and umami tastes, we utilized the Virtuous MultiTaste computational platform, which confirmed a subset of metabolite-sensory relationships. This study highlighted the importance of sensometrics in refining large metabolomics datasets to identify sensory-relevant compounds, ultimately advancing strategies to enhance the sensory quality and consumer acceptance of faba bean ingredients in plant-based food applications.

Consumer Preferences for Alternative Protein Sources in Northern and Eastern Europe: Insights to Support a Sustainable Food Transition

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It is widely recognised that the global food system must undergo a significant transformation in response to the climate emergency. The systems supporting meat consumption alone are responsible for nearly a fifth of current global greenhouse gas emissions and contribute to the rising incidence of diet-related non-communicable diseases. One strategy to mitigate the environmental and health impacts of animal-based foods is the development of foods based on alternative proteins (APs). Their potential role in promoting sustainable gely depends on consumer acceptance, which varies across regions and consumer groups. This variation is evident in Europe, where animal-based foods have long been embedded in food cultures, shaped not only by nutritional and agricultural needs but also by cultural identity. As result of the common EU Market, dietary patterns have started to converge, although regional differences remain, creating diverse starting points for consumer acceptance of APs and different approaches to encourage dietary change. Therefore, it is essential to understand what consumers, especially in Northern and Eastern European countries with traditionally higher meat and dairy consumption, value in terms of sources of APs. In this context, the objective of this study, as part of the EU-funded project LOCALITY, is to explore consumer preferences for different sources of alternative proteins in seven Northern and Eastern European Countries.

Data were collected through an online survey conducted between November and December 2024. A total of 5,250 respondents (750 per country; 50% female) completed the questionnaire, which included sociodemographic variables, attitudes, and expectations toward alternative protein sources. The AP categories assessed were plant-based fermented proteins, cultivated proteins, fungi-based proteins, algae-based proteins, insect-based proteins, and extruded plant-based proteins.

Fermented plant-based proteins were the most preferred alternative protein source (32%), followed by cultivated proteins (23%) and extruded plant-based proteins (18%). Fungi- and algae-based proteins accounted for 14% and 8% respectively, while insect-based proteins were least preferred (3%).

These findings suggest a favourable context for other EU-funded initiatives such as the HealthFerm project. The strong acceptance of fermented plant-based proteins—particularly in Northern and Eastern Europe—validates the Healthferm direction and positions it to play a crucial role in promoting the importance of fermented foods in the sustainable and healthy food transition happening across Europe.

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Unraveling the functional potential of microbial resources and pulse-based matrices for sourdough breadmaking

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Pulses are plant-based nutrient-rich substrates that support resilient and sustainable agricultural systems. This study aimed to optimize sourdough preparation from pulse-based substrates (specifically faba bean flour, faba bean protein concentrate, and yellow pea flour) by using binary consortia of lactic acid bacteria and yeasts for developing new bread formulations. A total of 288 type-II sourdoughs were created by varying the types of flour substrates and fermentation times. Seventeen of these type-II sourdoughs were identified as best performing based on optimal sourdough criteria. The transition to type-IV sourdoughs marked a critical enhancement in their fermentation maturity and functionality. Six most-promising pulse-based type-IV sourdoughs were selected as tailored inoculum for sourdough breadmaking, resulting in breads with significant biochemical differences compared to control wholewheat bread made with baker's yeasts. Pulse-based sourdough breads had higher total protein content and improved amino acid profiles. The interaction between *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* in yellow pea flour led to the lowest levels of anti-nutrients.

Although the *in vitro* protein digestibility was generally lower in all sourdough breads, the co-culture of *Levilactobacillus namurensis* and *Torulaspora delbrueckii* enhanced protein quality regardless of the flour compositions. Additionally, pulse-based sourdoughs enriched the bread with health-promoting bioactive compounds such as catechin, rutin, epicatechin, sinapic acid, and quercetin. Despite most sourdough breads exhibited less desirable textural characteristics, they showed more complex and diverse volatile organic compound profiles than the control bread.

Insights into the impact of sourdough and breadmaking process parameters on health-related aspects of wholemeal wheat bread

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Bread is a fermented, plant-based staple in Europe and is enjoyed worldwide. Using sourdough for leavening instead of just baker's yeast may increase the modification of wheat components in bread. It is suggested that this could lower the glycaemic index, boost the prebiotic effect, and reduce levels of anti-nutritional compounds in bread. However, conflicting findings in scientific studies highlight the need to understand how sourdough may improve the health-related properties of sourdough-type bread compared to yeast-leavened bread. Therefore, this study aimed to assess the influence of the sourdough consortium and the breadmaking process on the health-related properties of wholemeal sourdough-type bread versus yeast-leavened bread. Accordingly, wholemeal wheat sourdoughs made with strains of *Fructilactobacillus sanfranciscensis* and *Maudiozyma humilis*, *Pediococcus pentosaceus* and *M. humilis*, or *Companilactobacillus crustorum* and *Wickerhamomyces anomalus*, alongside baker's yeast, were used in two breadmaking processes (total fermentation times of 100 and 530 minutes). The specific volume (1.57-2.90 mL/g), pH (4.1-6.2), total titratable acidity (3.6-11.9 mL of 0.1 M NaOH), water-extractable arabinoxylan levels (WE-AX of 0.64-1.23% dm), and phytic acid breakdown (free-to-total phosphorus ratio of 0.54-0.75) of different bread types were influenced by the sourdough used and the process employed. Despite these variations, *in vitro* starch digestion reached a plateau after 30 minutes for all bread types, with slightly, but insignificantly, more resistant starch present in long-fermented bread made with *C. crustorum* and *W. anomalus* sourdough (10.9 % of total starch) compared to bread with baker's yeast (7.1 % of total starch). In contrast, higher soluble fibre levels were observed in wholemeal bread prepared with a long fermentation. Interestingly, long-fermented bread with *C. crustorum* and *W. anomalus* sourdough contained the highest levels of WE-AX. Finally, phytic acid was enzymatically broken down during breadmaking, but to a greater extent in long-fermented bread leavened with sourdough than with baker's yeast. This research demonstrates that both sourdough addition and the duration of the breadmaking process influence the biochemical composition of bread. The long-fermented sourdough bread, particularly that made with *C. crustorum* and *W. anomalus*, stood out due to the high level of flour component transformation. Consequently, the combination of ingredients and processing methods could further enhance the health-related properties of wholemeal bread. These findings enhance our understanding of the influence of sourdough addition and processing on bread properties, and urge the need for well-designed *in vivo* studies to study their impact on starch digestion rate, colon fermentability, and mineral bioavailability.

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Local Grains, Global Gains: Reinventing Tempeh with Nordic Faba Beans and Oat

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Securing resilient food systems requires developing sustainable, nutritious protein sources from locally available crops. Traditional tempeh depends on imported soybeans, limiting its use in northern regions. This study explored a tempeh-like product using Nordic-grown faba beans and whole-grain oats—climate-resilient, nutrient-rich crops—processed through microbial pre-treatment and solid-state fermentation (SSF) with *Rhizopus oligosporus*. Raw, pre-treated, and fermented materials were analyzed for macronutrients, fiber, starch fractions, and anti-nutritional compounds (phytic acid, raffinose-family oligosaccharides, vicine, and convicine). In vitro protein digestibility (INFOGEST), starch degradation, and viscosity were assessed alongside microscopy to evaluate matrix disruption and nutrient bioaccessibility. SSF increased protein content, free amino acids, and digestibility while reducing starch hydrolysis, suggesting a lower glycemic response. Anti-nutritional compounds were reduced by up to 90%. Microscopy confirmed enhanced fiber structure and cell wall breakdown. Oat inclusion improved texture and sensory quality, with consumer tests (n = 107, Sweden and Finland) favoring the oat–faba bean variant over faba bean-only. These findings highlight the potential of fermentation and pre-treatment strategies to improve the nutritional quality and acceptability of plant-based foods tailored to northern food systems.

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